

HEPATOCELLULAR CARCINOMA COMPLICATING LIVER CIRRHOSIS: A CASE REPORT WITH EMPHASIS ON VASCULAR INVOLVEMENT

N.M. Djuraeva¹, A.I. Ikramov², Kh.V. Abdukhalimova³, D.X. Hursanova⁴, M.A.
Kholmirzaev⁵

Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Surgery Named After
Academician V. Vakhidov^{1,2,3,4,5}

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Abstract. *Background:* Liver is the second largest organ in human body. There are lots of functions of this organ, including helping blood to clot, cleansing the blood of toxins, converting food into nutrients, to control hormone levels, fighting infections and illness, regenerating back after injury and metabolizing cholesterol, glucose, iron and controlling their levels [1].

Liver cirrhosis is the final stage of chronic liver disease characterized by the progressive scarring of liver tissue, which impairs liver function. The most common causes of cirrhosis include chronic viral infections (hepatitis B and C), excessive alcohol use, non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) and autoimmune diseases. As cirrhosis progresses, normal liver architecture is replaced by fibrous tissue, which disrupts blood flow through the liver, leading to a range of complications such as portal hypertension, ascites, and hepatic encephalopathy [2].

Hepatocellular Carcinoma (HCC): Hepatocellular carcinoma is the most common type of primary liver cancer, typically occurring in the setting of chronic liver disease. Cirrhosis is a major risk factor for developing HCC. The mechanism behind this association is thought to be the result of long-term liver inflammation, which leads to genetic mutations and liver cell regeneration, creating an environment conducive to the development of cancer. HCC can also be associated with chronic viral infections like hepatitis B and C, as well as with metabolic diseases such as NAFLD [3].

Case Presentation: A 65- years old patient was investigated on CT tomography, angiography triple phase of liver, in CT and MRI department of republican specialized center of surgery named after academician V. Vakhidov on date 6/01/2025 with the chief complaints of sudden inspiratory dyspnea, pain in the chest and right hypochondrium, abdominal distension and pedal edema, unreasonable fever for 8 days, gastrointestinal bleeding due to complications like portal hypertension, fatigue, jaundice. Physical examination revealed hepatomegaly and wheezing in the lungs.

Diagnosis: After the investigation was conducted, final conclusion confirmed as cirrhosis of liver with hepatocellular carcinoma, with the complications of portal and proper hepatic veins thrombosis with transition to the diaphragmatic part of the inferior caval vein, right atrium and finally pulmonary embolism. Patient was not having any history of communicable disease or any hereditary disease. However, he has been suffering from hepatitis types B and D for many years. In addition, he has history of hypertension and type II Diabetes mellitus for 12 years.

Conclusion: Cirrhosis of the liver with hepatocellular carcinoma is one of the final stages of liver disease with tumor. It is a serious condition, scarring and permanent damage to the liver. Life expectancy depends on the stage and type of cirrhosis of liver. Cirrhosis progresses more and

more scar tissue forms. Making it difficult for the liver to function (decompensate cirrhosis). If liver cirrhosis is diagnosed early and the cause is treated, further damage and complications can be limited and rarely reversed. In order to complete this triple phase CT angiography of liver is a golden standard.

Keywords: liver damage, Hepatocellular carcinoma, CT angiography triple phase of liver.

Introduction

Cirrhosis is a state that appears as a response of liver damage. It is characterized by destructions of normal liver tissue and it replaced by fibrous bands of tissue and nodules of regenerating liver tissue. However, in many cases instead of these regenerating nodules we may find dysplastic liver nodes. Chronic liver disease is a progressive deterioration of liver functions for more than six months, which includes synthesis of clotting factors, other proteins. Detoxification of harmful products of metabolism and excretion of bile. Chronic liver disease is a continuous process of inflammation, destruction and regeneration of liver parenchyma, which leads to fibrosis and cirrhosis. It is late stage of scarring of tissue of the liver caused by various forms of liver diseases such as chronic alcoholism and hepatitis. Liver is damaged whether by diseases, excessive alcohol consumption or another because it tries to repair itself.

Hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is a common cancer worldwide and currently the third leading cause of cancer- related deaths.

Classification of hepatocellular carcinoma.

BCLC (Barcelona Clinic Liver Cancer) — the most commonly used and widespread classification of HCC takes into account the extent of the tumor process, liver function, the patient's objective condition, and the expected effectiveness of treatment. The disease is divided into five stages:

Very early stage (BCLC 0) — A solitary tumor less than 2 cm in diameter.

Early stage or BCLC A — A solitary liver tumor of any size, or no more than 3 nodules with a maximum size of up to 3 cm, without involvement of major liver vessels and neighboring anatomical structures, in the absence of tumor-specific symptoms, with a satisfactory objective condition (ECOG = 0), and preserved liver function.

Intermediate stage or BCLC B — Cases of isolated, asymptomatic multiple liver tumors without macrovascular invasion, in patients with a satisfactory condition (ECOG = 0) and preserved liver function.

Advanced stage or BCLC C — Symptomatic HCC that worsens the objective condition (ECOG = 1-2), with a tumor of any size combined with or without invasion of major hepatic vessels and/or extrahepatic spread, but with preserved liver function.

Terminal stage (BCLC D) — Cases of disease with significant deterioration of the objective condition (tumor/cirrhosis), decompensated cirrhosis (Child-Pugh class C). However, in the presence of a small tumor (solitary < 5 cm or no more than 3 nodules < 3 cm), and meeting the so-called Milan criteria, orthotopic liver transplantation may be possible.

Case Report

Patient Present History

A 65- years old patient was admitted on CT tomography, angiography triple phase of liver, in CT and MRI department of republican specialized center of surgery named after academician V. Vakhidov on date 6/01/2025 with the chief complaints of sudden inspiratory dyspnea, pain in

the chest and right hypochondrium, abdominal distension and pedal edema, unreasonable fever for 8 days. After admission in hospital all investigations are done including blood test and CT angiography triple phase of liver, final conclusion confirmed as cirrhosis of liver with hepatocellular carcinoma, with the complications of portal and proper hepatic veins thrombosis with transition to the diaphragmatic part of the inferior caval vein, right atrium and finally pulmonary embolism in the area of where right pulmonary arteries divided into 2 branches.

Past History (History of past illness)

Patient was not having any history of communicable disease or any hereditary disease. Nevertheless, he has been suffering from hepatitis types B and D for many years. In addition, he has history of hypertension and type II Diabetes mellitus for 12 years. Bleeding Episodes: he has experienced episodes of upper gastrointestinal bleeding. No prior history of liver surgery or transplant.

History of life (Anamnesis vitae)

The patient was born and raised in countryside. He does not hold a higher education degree, worked in farm and retired 8 years ago. The patient is a smoker and has a history of alcohol consumption for many years.

Family History

The patient has a family history of liver disease, with chronic hepatitis, cirrhosis and liver cancer present in a first-degree relative, obviously both his siblings and parents.

Status Praesens (Current Condition)

General Condition:

The patient is conscious, oriented to time, place, and self.

General condition: non-satisfactory

General Appearance: The patient appears to be chronically ill with obvious jaundice.

Physical Examination:

Body type: Age-typical constitution. No signs of overweight (BMI=23)

Vital Signs: Blood pressure [150x90], heart rate [95], respiratory rate [43], temperature [38.5].

Abdomen: Tender liver, moderate ascites, palpable spleen.

Skin: Jaundice noted.

Extremities: Pitting edema in the lower limbs.

Neurological: not severe signs of hepatic encephalopathy at this time of examination.

Laboratory Findings:

Laboratory Test	Normal Range	Findings in Cirrhosis and HCC
Liver Function Tests (LFTs)		
Alanine aminotransferase (ALT)	7–56 U/L	200 U/L Elevated in cirrhosis and HCC due to liver cell damage
Aspartate aminotransferase (AST)	10–40 U/L	150 U/L Elevated in cirrhosis and HCC, higher AST to ALT ratio may suggest cirrhosis

Laboratory Test	Normal Range	Findings in Cirrhosis and HCC
Alkaline phosphatase (ALP)	44–147 U/L	180 U/L Mildly elevated in cirrhosis, may be elevated with HCC due to bile duct involvement
Total Bilirubin	0.1–1.2 mg/dL	20 mg/dL Elevated, particularly in cirrhosis and with jaundice
Direct (Conjugated) Bilirubin	0–0.3 mg/dL	12 mg/dL Elevated in cirrhosis and HCC, indicating cholestasis
Albumin	3.5–5.0 g/dL	2.6 g/dL Decreased due to impaired synthetic liver function in cirrhosis
Prothrombin Time (PT)	11–13.5 seconds	15 seconds Prolonged due to impaired liver function in cirrhosis and HCC
International Normalized Ratio (INR)	0.8–1.1	1.5 Elevated in cirrhosis and HCC, indicating clotting impairment
Hepatic Synthetic Function		
Ammonia	15–45 µmol/L	53 µmol/L Elevated in cirrhosis if hepatic encephalopathy is present
Lactate Dehydrogenase (LDH)	140–280 U/L	320 U/L Elevated in HCC due to tumor cell breakdown
Alpha-fetoprotein (AFP)	<10 ng/mL	40 ng/mL Elevated in HCC, especially in the presence of cirrhosis
Complete Blood Count (CBC)		
White Blood Cell Count (WBC)	4,500–11,000 cells/µL	17,000 cells/µL elevated
Hemoglobin (Hb)	13.8–17.2 g/dL (male)	10 g/dL Decreased if there is anemia from liver disease or bleeding
Platelet Count	150,000–450,000/µL	680 /µL
Hepatitis Serology		

Laboratory Test	Normal Range	Findings in Cirrhosis and HCC
Hepatitis B Surface Antigen (HBsAg)	Negative	Positive
HIV Antibody	Negative	Negative

Instrumental Diagnostic Methods: Multislice Computed Tomography (MSCT) Angiography triple phase of liver.

A) Native Phase (axial slice)

B) Arterial Phase (axial slice)

Figure 1. The liver is deformed. The contours are clear, but uneven and nodular in places. The parenchymal structure is heterogeneous. In the right and partially in the left lobes of the liver, with partial extra-organ spread into the subdiaphragmatic space and deformation of the contour of the right dome, an irregularly shaped, multi-nodular mass is observed. The mass has relatively clear, uneven contours and measures 10.2 x 10.7 x 9.5 cm (anteroposterior x width x height), with a heterogeneous structure and a density of +20 to +45 HU in the native phase (A). During contrast enhancement, heterogeneous contrast agent accumulation is observed in the arterial phase (B), with a density of +32 to +76 HU. Branches from both the right and left hepatic arteries are identified within the mass.

A) Venous Phase (axial slice)

B) Delayed Phase (axial slice)

Figure 2. In the venous phase, the density is +30 to +98 HU. In the delayed phase, the formation is iso-hypodense compared to the liver parenchyma.

Figure 3.

A) Portal Phase (coronal slice). The portal vein s thrombosed with extension to the lobar and segmental branches. Collaterals up to 5 mm are identified in the porta hepatic. This is called tumor thrombus in the portal vein.

B) In the area of the right pulmonary artery branching, a contrast enhancement defect of 19.5 mm in width is identified, extending to the lobar and segmental branches. In the left pleural cavity, there is an effusion with a height of 2.8 cm in the axial plane, with collapse of the adjacent lung sections

Discussion

Cirrhosis of the liver with hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC) is an advanced and challenging stage of liver disease. It represents a combination of chronic liver injury and the development of malignant tumors in the liver, often in the context of pre-existing cirrhosis. This condition is characterized by significant liver dysfunction, which leads to the manifestation of various complications such as portal hypertension, ascites, gastrointestinal bleeding, and hepatic encephalopathy, all of which were observed in the presented case [4].

Hepatocellular carcinoma is strongly linked to cirrhosis, which is considered a major risk factor. The mechanism underlying this association involves chronic inflammation of the liver, which can lead to genetic mutations and abnormal liver regeneration. Over time, these factors create an environment conducive to the formation of malignant cells. In the case of chronic viral infections, such as hepatitis B and D, which were present in this patient's history, the risk of developing HCC increases significantly [5].

The patient described in this case report presented with several symptoms indicative of both liver cirrhosis and advanced HCC. These included sudden dyspnea, right hypochondrial pain, abdominal distension, pedal edema, and fever, all of which point to decompensated cirrhosis complicated by HCC. Imaging studies confirmed the presence of a large tumor mass with vascular invasion and thrombosis of the portal and hepatic veins, along with significant involvement of the inferior caval vein and right atrium, leading to pulmonary embolism. This multifocal involvement of vascular structures is a critical finding as it complicates treatment and worsens the prognosis.

The diagnosis of HCC in cirrhotic patients requires careful assessment, and imaging studies like CT and MRI play a crucial role. In this case, the triple-phase CT angiography of the liver was essential in delineating the tumor's characteristics and its involvement with surrounding vascular structures. The standard triple-phase approach—native, arterial, venous, and delayed phases—provides comprehensive information about tumor vascularity and the extent of any vascular invasion, such as portal vein thrombosis or hepatic vein involvement, which is often a hallmark of advanced disease. In this patient, the CT findings confirmed both tumor thrombus and extravascular extension, which posed a significant challenge for treatment planning [6].

The BCLC classification, which is widely used to stage HCC, highlights the importance of liver function in determining the appropriate management strategy. For patients like the one in this case, who present with terminal stage disease (BCLC D), liver transplantation may be a potential option if they meet specific criteria such as the Milan criteria, even in the presence of small tumors. However, the extensive vascular involvement seen in this patient makes this option unlikely. Palliative care remains the focus for such advanced cases, aimed at improving quality of life and managing symptoms, such as ascites and hepatic encephalopathy.

The prognosis of cirrhosis with HCC largely depends on the degree of liver function impairment, the extent of tumor spread, and the presence of extrahepatic metastasis or vascular involvement. In this case, the presence of extensive portal vein thrombosis and pulmonary embolism significantly worsens the prognosis. However, early diagnosis and appropriate management can help mitigate some of the liver dysfunction, and in rare cases, treatments such as liver transplantation or resection may offer extended survival for patients without widespread vascular invasion. The role of screening for HCC in patients with cirrhosis, especially those with a history of chronic viral hepatitis or NAFLD is crucial. Regular surveillance using imaging modalities like ultrasound and CT, alongside the measurement of serum markers like alpha-fetoprotein (AFP), can help detect HCC at earlier, more treatable stages. [7].

Conclusion

Liver cirrhosis with hepatocellular carcinoma represents an advanced stage of liver disease associated with a tumor. It is a severe condition that causes scarring and irreversible liver damage. Life expectancy largely depends on the stage and type of cirrhosis. As cirrhosis progresses, more scar tissue forms, impairing liver function (decompensated cirrhosis). If detected early and the underlying cause is addressed, further damage and complications can be prevented, and in rare cases, partially reversed. The gold standard for early evaluating this condition is a triple-phase CT angiography of the liver.

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